

HOLY PLACES AND SHRINES RESTORED IN BUKHARA DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract.

There are a huge number of ancient monuments in Bukhara. Each of them is valuable. Each one seems to breathe a breath of poetry. Each one seems to be a silent witness to what kind of people our ancestors were. The architectural monuments of Bukhara reflect the high intelligence of our ancestors. The Chor Minor ensemble in the city center is considered unique in the East. The Khoja Zayniddin and Baland mosques, and the Mir Arab madrasah are examples of high engineering, extraordinary art, and unparalleled beauty. You are certainly aware that for centuries the land of Uzbekistan has been one of the centers of the great and unique culture, science, and socio-economic development of the Muslim world. Ancient Uzbekistan, that is, the land of Movarunnahr, is a land of scholars and thinkers who made an unforgettable contribution to the development of the high culture and civilization of the Islamic world. Thanks to independence, large-scale landscaping work was carried out on the occasion of the anniversaries of Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, Khoja Ali Romitani, Sayyid Amir Kulal, Bahauddin Naqshband, and Abu Havs Kabir Bukhari.

Bukhara, known as the Venice of the East, has more than 140 major historical and architectural monuments. Among them are the Bukhara Arch, the Samanid Mausoleum, the Chashmai Ayyub Mausoleum, the Mag`oki Attori Mosque, the Namozgoh Mosque, the Poyi Kalon Ensemble, the Remains of the Fortress Wall, the Kalon Tower, the Kalon Mosque, the Mir Arab Madrasah, the Tim and Toqilar, the Labikhovuz Ensemble, the Ulugbek Madrasah, the Chor Minor, the Bolokhovuz Mosque, the Sitorai Mohi Khossa Ensemble and other monuments that fascinate tourists. Having preserved such ancient architectural monuments, Bukhara remains one of the most favorite places for tourists. Bukhara attracts the attention of millions of people from all over the world with its charm.

Renovation of the "Seven Pir" shrine in Bukhara during the years of independence.

Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani was born in 1103 in the city of Gijduvani. He grew up mastering knowledge and skills. He led Muslims to the right path and reached the level of sheikh. He was given many titles such as “Khojai Jahon”, “Qalb zikri sultani”, “Khojasi of the two worlds”, “Qutbi zamon”, “Afoqi zamon”. He founded the Hazrat Khojagon tariqat. There, he became the leader of the tariqat and engaged in the profession of “buz weaving”. The basis of the “Khojagon tariqat” was the Quran and hadith, fighting fiercely against bid’a-tu superstition, false pir-u-muridism, turning humanity away from greed and greed, encouraging them to earn a living through honest work, and sharing the sustenance given by Allah with many people. Hazrat Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani died in 1179 (some sources say 1220) in the city of Gijduvani, and his grave is located here.

Thanks to the independence, in 2003, on the occasion of the 900th anniversary of the birth of Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, large-scale landscaping work was carried out. In particular, a ten-column porch will be rebuilt above the grave of the saint. This was a symbolic sign that the saint was in tenth place in the Silsilai Sharif. A new mosque with a capacity of 1,500 people will be built next to the mausoleum, and a pond and well that were buried during the Soviet era will be restored. A beautiful 4-hectare avenue will be built around the mosque and the complex.

The second of the seven pirs, the shrine of "Khoja Muhammad Orif Revhari Mohitobon", is located in the Shafirkan district. The dahma in the shrine is surrounded by wood, and a white thorny plant grows above the grave of the saint without losing its whiteness. There were chillaharans on the qibla side of the shrine, and a long porch faced north, and on the upper side there was a large fruit garden. Many visitors came to visit and ate the fruits of this garden. Water was drunk from the large pond in front of the porch. The current three-sided porch in the shrine is very ancient. The second of the seven pirs, the shrine of "Khoja Muhammad Orif Revhari Mohitobon", is located in the Shafirkan district. The dahma in the shrine is surrounded by wood, and a white thorny plant grows above the grave of the saint without losing its whiteness. There were chillaharans on the qibla side of the shrine, and a long porch faced north, and on the upper side there was a large fruit garden. Many visitors came to visit and ate the fruits of this garden. Water was drunk from the large pond in front of the porch. The current three-sided porch in the shrine is very ancient.

The next destination is the “Khoja Mahmud Anjir Faghnavi” shrine in Vobkent district. The “Khoja Mahmud Anjir Faghnavi” shrine was neglected and in a very dilapidated state during the Soviet era. The mosque here was turned

into a collective farm warehouse. During the years of independence, reconstruction and improvement work was also carried out at this shrine. In 1999-2000, a two-story mausoleum was built on the grave of Khoja Mahmud Anjir Faghnavi, a new mosque with three porches that can accommodate 300 people, a pool, a gatehouse, a hotel, and a modern ablution facility were completed. In the courtyard of the mosque, ornamental and fruit trees were planted, and gardens were organized. All convenient conditions were created for those who come to visit and pray. The mosque was officially registered and began operating in 1998. Khoja Mahmud Anjir was the 12th ring leader in the Faghnavi silsilai-sharif, a disciple of Khoja Arif Mohitoban, and a teacher of Khoja Ali Romitani. They lived in the Vobkent region in the 13th century.

The fourth of the seven pirs is the shrine of “Khoja Ali Romitaniy” located in Romitan district. It is about 37 kilometers from Vobkent district. Khoja Ali Romitaniy (also known as Khojai Azizon) (Kurgan village, Romitan district-1195/1324) is a representative of the “Khojagon Naqshbandiy” order. He was engaged in weaving. He lived for a while in Khorezm, opened a khanaqo and spread the “Khojagon” order in this region. His spiritual mentor is Mahmud Anjir Faghnaviy. He, in turn, is the mentor of Khoja Muhammad Boboyi Samosiy.

The mosque named after “Khoja Ali Romitani” was built in 2004 using the Hashar method. It has a gatehouse, a mosque, a mausoleum and a porch built in the national style, a pool and a stone fountain, a hotel and kitchens. In addition, there are two hotels, a well and a special garden with fruit trees around the mosque. Friday prayers, Ramadan and Eid al-Adha prayers are performed in this mosque in the village of Kurgan. There are ablution rooms for men and women for worshipers. Skilled carvers were invited, and in the fall of 2014 the tombstone in the “Khoja Ali Romitani” mausoleum was renovated. Currently, construction and landscaping work is underway.

Another pir in the Romitan district is Khoja Muhammad Boboyi Samosiy, a disciple of Khoja Ali Romitaniy. The shrine of Khoja Muhammad Boboyi Samosiy is located 5 kilometers from the shrine of Khoja Romitaniy. He was considered one of the great sheikhs of Bukhara and was known by the name of Hazrat Boboyi Samosiy. Hazrat Samosiy (in some sources "Simos") was born in the area where the mosque is located. The sources do not give his year of birth. His death falls on the year 1354.

The shrine of the sixth of the Pirs, “Sayyid Amir Kulol”, is located in the Yangi Hayot fortress of the Kagon district. It is about 47 kilometers from the Romitan district. The “Sayyid Amir Kulol” mosque is named after a historical

figure. Sayyid Amir Kulol (1281-1370) was the sixth of the seven Pirs of Bukhara and lived for 89 years. His real name was Sayyid Amir Kalon, and he was called Sayyid Amir Kulol because his profession was pottery.

The Sayyid Amir Kulol mosque was rebuilt in 1994 after independence. The mosque continues its activities to this day. There is an aviary on the front and right sides of the mosque building. There are 2 rooms on the right and left sides of the entrance to the building. The height of the mosque is 4.70 meters, length - 24.4 meters, width - 18.5 meters. The height of the mosque dome is 9 meters. The minaret of the mosque was built in 2007. The mausoleum of the Sayyid Amir Kulol mosque consists of 2 rooms, the first room is a reading room, and the second room houses the grave of Sayyid Amir Kulol. The mausoleum was built in 2007 in the national architectural style with a dome on the initiative of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov. The walls are made of baked bricks. The height of the mausoleum building is 12 meters, length is 15 meters, and width is 8 meters.

The world-famous shrine of Bahauddin Naqshband is located in the village of Qasri Orifon, Kagon district. It is 5 kilometers from the shrine of Sayyid Amir Kulal to this place. The shrine of Bahauddin Naqshband was formed over five hundred years. There is very little information about its early history. The first buildings in front of the tomb of Bahauddin Naqshband appeared approximately after the death of the saint. During architectural and archaeological research, the remains and foundations of the first buildings were found. Shortly after the death of Bahauddin Naqshband, a cemetery appeared on the western side of the tomb of the saint, where the murids-admirers of the saint began to be buried. Later, the "Dahmai Shahon" ("Cemetery of the Kings") appeared here, where representatives of the ruling dynasty of Bukhara were buried.

The appearance of the Bahauddin Naqshbandi shrine during the years of independence.

The achievements of our people during the glorious and victorious years of independence are countless, and each of them is worthy of centuries. All this indicates that our unique and united soul is steadfastly and boldly walking along the path of a great future for our Uzbekistan. Every Uzbek person should deeply understand these ongoing works, appreciate our independence and peace, and cherish peace and harmony in our country. After all, peace and harmony are the greatest blessings.

In 1993, on the occasion of the 675th anniversary of the birth of Bahauddin Naqshband, the importance of studying the teachings of Bahauddin Naqshband

in Uzbekistan increased. The Naqshbandiya Scientific Center was established at Bukhara State University. The study of mystical and mystical heritage was launched there. The Naqshbandiya Center was also established at the Bukhara State Museum-Reserve.

They say that flowers bloom at the feet of a virtuous person. The happiness of this blessed place was revealed when Islam Karimov visited the 675th anniversary of the birth of a great representative of the Islamic world, Bahauddin Naqshband, on September 16, 1993. During the years of independence, under the initiative and leadership of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, centuries-old creative work was carried out in a previously neglected place. Monuments buried many centuries ago have opened their eyes again. Guests who set foot here begin their pilgrimage, first of all, from the grave where the mother of the great scholar found eternal rest. The revival of this tradition alone symbolizes the respect for mothers in our nation.

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